

ENGLISH AS THE LANGUAGE OF INTERNATIONAL COMMUNICATION

Djalilova Dildora¹ Toshpo'latov Shavkat²

¹Teacher of Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute

²Student of Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6669583>

Annotation: The objective purpose of this article is to investigate language as the most important and central tool for communication. According to the perspective of youth on global communication, the usage of foreign languages is seen as fruitful for the best possible future and is especially widespread in modern life. Youth with different approaches, from different social groups, and with different living conditions tend to use the English language because English is currently a lingua franca. In order to achieve educational goals and general knowledge (or understanding), language is a guarantee for a better future, so almost all people learn speak foreign languages. There is no geographical or social distance in learning a foreign language among speakers. Language is a great and complex system which maintains its value and deserves respect.

Keywords: youth perspective, English language, foreign language learning, philosophy of language, globalization

INTRODUCTION

The study of any foreign language cannot be equated with the study of history or math because it involves adapting to certain customs and traditions of different social groups as well. Language is defined as a vocal system which is used by human beings to communicate with each other. Thus language is more than communication; it's a social action and functions to express thoughts. In most cases, language is a dominant leader and ruler of the dependent. People are also dependent on it.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Language mastering style is the way someone feel easy, comfort and save when they are learning. Sure, have some factors that influences to the learning style. They are psychological, sociological, teachers, emotional and environment. So, have the effect of learning style on the students' language achievement. Learning foreign languages will be influenced by their genetic make-up, their previous learning experiences, their culture and the society they live in .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Language depends on place. Moreover, in each place it may take on various structures and different usages. Different social groups speak even the same language differently. For example, communicative language and political speech language are mostly different from each other. Foreign language and its structure include a wide spectrum. Learning a foreign language and really

making it work will make us rich. It's true that language is a narrow band because for each sphere it has its own words in its vocabulary, its own structure, and its own environment or sphere.

What causes people to speak in other languages? Changing social and intellectual needs may affect the way people speak in other languages. Even when people change their living circumstances, in mixed surroundings they speak the foreign language which the environment demands.

For global communication, using an international language is the best way. Thus nowadays for most global communication the English language is widespread. The English language is mostly used among younger people as a method of communication. English language is divided into 2 parts: American English and British English. English has positive and negative sides; in fact, every language has its own benefits and drawbacks. The majority of the learners of the English language suffer from English grammar itself. They think that knowing only words or vocabulary is enough. However, they think in a wrong way, because tense forms, expressions, etc. are essential. The value of the language decreases when one does not know its grammar. Some young people even think that some grammar rules are completely unnecessary for speaking. This attitude is proof of their distaste for grammar. The majority of phrasal verbs and idioms are not convenient for them to learn. Most of them think that while they are speaking they will forget these phrasal verbs and so they do not even try to use them. Those who understand that these are a colorful side of the English language use them in writing and speaking.

In the English language, especially in its American version, some phonetical changes and lexical innovations appeared and the language's lexical structure was enriched. It's a fact that, in the countries where English is being used, economical and cultural developments occur first as a result of relationships with other countries, also raising indicators such as scientific-cultural, economic, and public/political developments with the help of the English language. Everything depends on humans. The creators and the carriers of the language are humans. French linguist Jan Van Die's idea would be appropriate to mention here. He claims that "... for creating a language human's thinking should be enhanced..." . However, the author was not satisfied with this provision. According to that quote, supposedly, the first human's thinking developed after humans created a language. The author argues that both language and thinking were developed and formed together in a parallel vein. The author thinks that there is no practical and scientific explanation for the creation of language and

thought. Language is not abstract, it is systematic. It is formed systematically and acts phonetically, grammatically and with lexical structure.

From the perspective of youth in the Modern Period, the English language has turned into a register used for political talks or negotiations, and even into a business language. Scientific and medical researchers also use English. According to international agreements, even on airplanes, workers must know English. The English language has become an official language in more than 75 countries all around the world. It is commonly known that a few hundred years ago as a result of invasions of Britain, the English language became a language. In Old English, there used to be many words borrowed from the French language. For example: “damage,” “marriage,” “ambulance,” “jury,” “parliament,” “justice,” etc. (4) It is difficult to understand Old English. Writings that were written in Old English can only be read by experts. Young people do not read Old English materials but they use some words without knowing that they belong to the English period, the period in which the “Beowulf” poem was written. The Middle English language looks like Modern English, so it is not so difficult to understand .

CONCLUSION

To conclude this article, young people understand that it is important to learn foreign languages for their futures prospects. Knowledge of foreign languages means knowledge of other countries or their cultures, identities, histories, etc. Notwithstanding all difficulties and barriers, all negative and positive sides, whether with an attitude of hate or love or under compulsion, young people learn and develop their foreign language skills. Even for global communication, foreign languages are essential. Languages are a main factor in nation building. When a language is in decline, the nation is in decline as well. We must respect other languages. If we do not respect other languages, we should not expect mutual respect for our mother tongue.

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